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Regular research paper

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EFFECT OF YOUNG MIDFIELD SHELTERBELTS DEVELOPMENT ON SPECIES RICHNESS OF MACROFUNGI COMMUNITIES AND THEIR FUNCTIONAL STRUCTURE

ABSTRACT: The aim of the study was to recognize features characterizing development of macrofungi communities occurring in afforestations planted in crop fields and to evaluate the role of these habitats in conservation of macrofungi and preserve high species richness. The study was carried out in 1998–2006 and covered four shelterbelts (planted in 1993–1996) located in the area of the Dezydery Chłapowski Landscape Park (western part of Poland). The shelterbelts were colonized by macrofungi just after planting. During first years of their growth a total of 174 species were recorded. Species composition changed significantly between initial (1998–2000) and final (2004–2006) period of study. Similarity of macrofungi communities (expressed as the Sørensen's index) between these two periods in studied shelterbelts ranged between 37 and 46%. In spite of high similarity in tree species composition between studied afforestations (69–80%), the communities of macrofungi differed strongly between these sampling plots (Sørensen's index was equal to about 40%). Pattern of changes in percentage share of functional groups, i.e. parasitic, mycorrhizal and saprotrophs (humicolous, lignicolous, litter-inhibiting and muscicolous ones) in individual afforestations was different but the diversity of the communities measured with the Shannon-Weaver H' index on the basis of share of functional groups tended to increase with ageing of afforestations. On average, the share of fungi

growing on soil (ectomycorrhizal and humicolous saprotrophic species) was highest among all distinguished groups. Species composition of particular functional group was changing during the study period. A species representing new groups (lignicolous saprotrophs and parasites) were appearing in some shelterbelts in successive years. There were recorded some species rare in Poland, eg. *Psilocybe* (*Stropharia*) *melanosperma* (Bull. ex Pers.: Fr.) Noordel., *Clavariadelphus fistulosus* (Holmsk.: Fr.) Corner, *Thelephora caryophyllea* (Schaeff.): Fr., *Agrocybe arvalis* (Fr.) Singer, *Galerina clavata* (Velen.) Kühner, *Lachnella alboviolascens* (Alb. & Schwein.: Fr.) Fr., *Macrocystidia cucumis* f. *minor* Joss, *Mycena amicta* (Fr.) Quél., *Psilocybe* (*Stropharia*) *inuncta* (Fr.: Fr.) Noordel., *Trichophaea gregaria* (Rehm) Boud. and *Typhula filata* (Pers.) Herter. Occurrence of rare and threatened species in young shelterbelts indicates that such afforestations, planted in crop fields but not treated by agricultural practices, contribute to the protection of species richness of macrofungi associated with tree communities and they are important substitute habitats for many species.

KEY WORDS: agricultural landscape, shelterbelts, macrofungi, functional groups, biodiversity

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the key approaches to the protection of biodiversity in arable land is the preservation of the existing habitats and introduction of a number of ecosystems not used in agriculture (Ryszkowski and Bałazy 1991, Karg and Ryszkowski 1996, Ryszkowski 1998, 2001, Ryszkowski *et al.* 2002, Pullin 2005, Zajaczkowski 2005). Shelterbelts planted in crop fields are an important component of the agricultural landscape in the Polish Lowland as they perform important functions maintaining a high resistance of the landscape to the threats caused by farming (Karg and Karlik 1993, Bałazy *et al.* 1998, Ryszkowski *et al.* 1999, Ryszkowski *et al.* 2003, Zajaczkowski 2005). In the 1990s, several ten kilometers of shelterbelts were planted in arable fields located in the Gen. Dezydery Chłapowski Landscape Park (Poznań Province, West Poland), and studies were initiated on the role of shelterbelts from the time of their introduction (Kujawa 1998, Karg 1999, Ryszkowski *et al.* 2003). Most often, the studies on the role of midfield afforestations in a farmland were concentrated upon producers – mainly vascular plants (Ratyńska 2002, Bernacki 2004), and primary and secondary consumers (Barczak *et al.* 2002, Karg *et al.* 2003, Szanser 2003, Kajak and Oleszczuk 2004, Karg 2004, Kujawa 2004, Łęcki 2004, Makulec 2004, Nowak 2004, Olechowicz 2004, Olejniczak 2004, Sobczyk 2004, Szeplińska 2004, Wasilewska 2004). Few studies concerned decomposers – consumers of dead organic matter (Wojewoda and Russel 2003), although this group of organisms performs an important role in each ecosystem.

Our studies were conducted in shelterbelts planted in arable land and concerned macrofungi communities¹ occurring in young afforestations. The present paper summarizes the results of the study on initial stage of the colonization of shelterbelts with these organisms. Fungi are the most important decomposers of cellulose, chitin, and lignin debris. Thus, their presence determines the rate and course of mineralization and humification of organic matter (Orłóś

1966, Arnolds 1992a, Dix and Webster 1995). Fungi, especially ectomycorrhizal species, are responsible for the normal growth of trees (their mycorrhizal partners). Thus, their presence is necessary in the developing plant communities, especially those man-made ones, planted on non-forest soils (Arnolds 1992a, Rudawska 2000, Kałucka 2001).

Fungal succession in plant communities is going along the succession of vegetation (Arnolds 1992a, Kałucka 2001). According to our knowledge, in Poland and abroad long-term studies on macrofungi occurring in shelterbelts planted in crop fields are almost absent. In Poland the only study was carried out in 1998–2000, in which the species composition of fungi was examined on three 400 m² plots established in one of the young shelterbelts and in two old ones (about 150 years old) (Strakulska 2001, Lisiewska and Strakulska 2002). Spontaneous secondary succession was observed in tree stands growing in former crop fields located in the area of potential coniferous forest habitat near the Białowieża Primeval Forest (Kałucka 2001).

The aim of our study was to recognize features of macrofungi community development in young midfield afforestations, especially concerning the number of species and share of their functional groups and the changes occurring with the development of afforestations. The role of shelterbelts in the protection of the species diversity of fungi in the agricultural landscape was evaluated as well, especially with respect to recognition of the importance of afforestations as substitute habitats for rare and threatened species of fungi.

2. STUDY AREA

The study was conducted in four shelterbelts named S-3, S-4, S-5a, S-5b, where numbers denote age of shelterbelt (in years) at the beginning of study. The shelterbelts were planted during 1993–1996 in arable land located in the Gen. Dezydery Chłapowski Landscape Park, Poznań Province, West Poland (Ryszkowski *et al.* 2003) (Table 1). These were longitudinal shelterbelts connect-

¹ The term “fungal community” means here (after Arnolds 1992): “any concrete assemblage of fungi that grows together in a certain uniform space, independent of its size and degree of heterogeneity in terms of habitat exploitation and substrate preference”.

Table 1. Main features of studied shelterbelts. Numbers followed the shelterbelt names (S-3, S-4, S-5a, S-5b) denote age of shelterbelt (in years) at the beginning of study. At tree species names their percentage cover is given; “+” denotes occurrence of single trees.

Shelterbelt code, time of planting, dimensions, area	No. of tree species	Tree cover and height of highest trees at the beginning (1998) and end (2006) of study	Herb layer cover and share of grasses (%) at the beginning (1998) and end (2006) of study
S-5a (Dec 1993) 340 m × 18m, 0.6 ha	18	1998 – 60%, 3 m 2006 – 100%, 14 m	1998 – 100, 40 2006 – 80, 50
Tree species composition: <i>Larix</i> sp. (30), <i>Picea abies</i> (25), <i>Pinus sylvestris</i> (10), <i>Betula pendula</i> (10), <i>Populus</i> (5), <i>Quercus</i> sp. (5), <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> (5), <i>Ulmus minor</i> (5), <i>Sorbus intermedia</i> (1), <i>Sorbus aucuparia</i> (1), <i>Tilia cordata</i> (1), <i>Acer platanoides</i> (1), <i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i> (1), <i>Carpinus betulus</i> (+), <i>Pyrus communis</i> (+), <i>Prunus insititia</i> (+), <i>Salix</i> sp. (+)			
S-5b (Dec 1993) 400 m × 16m, 0.6 ha	12	1998 – 50%, 3 m 2006 – 60%, 14 m	1998 – 100, 70 2006 – 100, 90
Tree species composition: <i>Larix</i> sp. (30), <i>Pinus sylvestris</i> (30), <i>Picea abies</i> (30), <i>Fraxinus excelsior</i> (5), <i>Quercus</i> sp. (1), <i>Betula pendula</i> (1), <i>Tilia cordata</i> (1), <i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i> (1), <i>Acer platanoides</i> (1), <i>Ulmus minor</i> (+), <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> (+), <i>Sorbus intermedia</i> (+)			
S-4 (March 1995) 230 m × 19.5m, 0.4 ha	12	1998 – 30%, 2 m 2006 – 50%, 14 m	1998 – 100, 70 2006 – 100, 100
Tree species composition: <i>Picea abies</i> (40), <i>Fraxinus excelsior</i> (20), <i>Quercus</i> sp. (10), <i>Alnus glutinosa</i> (10), <i>Ulmus minor</i> (5), <i>Fagus sylvatica</i> (5), <i>Populus</i> sp. (5), <i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i> (5), <i>Sorbus intermedia</i> (+), <i>Acer platanoides</i> (+), <i>Salix</i> sp. (+)			
S-3 (April 1996) 400 m × 10m, 0.4 ha	11	1998 – 50%, 2 m 2006 – 90%, 14 m	1998 – 100, 50 2006 – 90, 60
Tree species composition: <i>Larix</i> sp. (25), <i>Populus</i> sp. (20), <i>Betula pendula</i> (10), <i>Picea abies</i> (15), <i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i> (10), <i>Ulmus minor</i> (10), <i>Quercus</i> sp. (5), <i>Fraxinus excelsior</i> (5), <i>Sorbus intermedia</i> (+), <i>Sorbus aucuparia</i> (+), <i>Acer negundo</i> (+)			

ing a forest complex (80 ha) near the village of Turew and small woodlots growing in crop fields. The studied shelterbelts were planted in typical arenic hapludalf soils which prevail in the area of Turew (Marcinek 1996). Tree species composition in these shelterbelts was similar (Sørensen's index was equal to 69–80%). At the same time, interdisciplinary studies were carried out on their role as windbreaks, and on the communities of different organisms living there (Ryszkowski *et al.* 2003).

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The species composition of macrofungi was examined in 1998–2006 at regular intervals of 3–4 weeks from April until November. Each year, 8–9 surveys were performed (total of 79), which covered whole area of studied

shelterbelts. All the fungi of the classes Ascomycetes and Basidiomycetes producing fruit bodies were noted. For the analysis of changes in community structure six functional (biotrophic) groups of species were distinguished as in the papers by Keizer (1993) and Friedrich (2001): parasitic (P), mycorrhizal (M/s), saprotrophic: humicolous (soil) (S/s), lignicolous (wood) (S/w), litter-inhabiting (S/l) and muscicolous ones (S/ms).

Analysis of the differences in fungi community structure between the shelterbelts and their changes were performed in double way:

- Effect of plant cover structure and atmospheric precipitation on species number was studied with regard to number of species recorded in single, consecutive years.

- The analysis of changes in species composition of fungal communities and

their structure was done with regard to total number of species recorded during three successive years. Such approach results from commonly accepted rule that representative data on fungi occurring in a place, based on recording of fruit bodies, should cover several years. Depending on frequency of field controls recommended duration time varies from 3 to 6 years (Arnolds 1992b, Keizer 1993, Friedrich 2000). Because growing afforestations are characterized by dynamic changes of biocenoses, the analysis of changes in fungal communities was performed with regard to total number of species observed in three-year periods. First period covered shelterbelt age of 3–5 years, second one – 4–6 years, third one – 5–7 years and so on. Due to such approach, the possibility of recognition of the changes in fungal communities was obtained, taking into account demand of collecting data during several years (three years in this case).

Communities of macrofungi were characterized with the use of total species number, species number of functional groups, the percentage share of these groups in community and Shannon-Weaver diversity index H' . Similarity in macrofungi species composition between the periods and between the shelterbelts was quantified with the Sørensen's similarity index (Dice 1945). When analyzing the relationship between species number and atmospheric precipitation, total precipitation in period of performing observation was taken into account, i.e. from April until November.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Number of species

Total of 174 taxons were noted in all shelterbelts, including 156 Basidiomycetes and 18 Ascomycetes. Of that, 132 taxons were determined to species-level, and 38 – to genus-level. Most species were of the genera *Psathyrella* (10 species), *Conocybe* (9), *Inocybe* (9), *Mycena* (9) and *Clitocybe* (6). Significant number of species belonged to a group of species associated with ruderal vegetation, meadows, and agrocenoses, for example *Agrocybe dura* (Bolt.: Fr.) Singer, *A. praecox* (Pers.: Fr.) P. Kumm., *A. pediades*

(Fr.) Fayod, *Cyathus olla* (Batsch): Pers. This observation is consistent with the results by Lisiewska and Strakulska (2002) who stated that significant share of ubiquitous species of fungi is characteristic for midfield afforestations.

Shelterbelts planted in crop fields were colonized by macrofungi as early as in the first years but their initial number of species (in first year of the study) differed strongly between the shelterbelts. It ranged from 2 to 16 species per shelterbelt (Table 2). Most likely they were dependent mainly on different pattern of herb layer development occurring in studied shelterbelts (Table 1). Small number of species was recorded in the shelterbelts S-4 and S-5b (2 and 3, respectively), which in whole study period was characterized by high degree of herb layer cover and by strong grass domination (70–100%), which formed very dense and compact cover.

Such pattern of herb layer growth did not favour development of macrofungi. Previously, attention to occurrence of such regularity was paid by Lisiewska and Strakulska (2002). Furthermore, dense sward hinders to find out fruit bodies, what also could affect low number of species recorded.

In the other two shelterbelts with lower share of grasses in herb layer (40–60%) the number of species was markedly higher (15–16 species). Noticeable differences between the two pairs of the shelterbelts remained over whole study period (Table 2). Number of species observed in shelterbelts with high dominance of grasses amounted to 2–21 species per shelterbelt per year (on average – 11.9) while in shelterbelts with lower share of grasses – 15–43 species per shelterbelt per year (on average – 25.9). The difference was statistically significant (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 16$, $N = 18$, $P < 0.0001$). In the poorest shelterbelt, 38 species of fungi were noted over 8 years, whereas 108 species in the richest one.

The differences between shelterbelts were not related to their age – the number of species observed in two 5-year old shelterbelts differed more than 5-times (3 and 16 species recorded). Furthermore, as many as 15 species were found in the youngest (3-year old) shelterbelt – that is only one species less than in 5-year old shelterbelt.

Table 2. Species number of fungi recorded in shelterbelts in 1998–2006. S-3, S-4, S-5a, S-5b – see Table 1.

Year	S-3	S-4	S-5a	S-5b
1998	15	2	16	3
1999	19	6	26	12
2000	32	21	40	16
2001	30	14	41	16
2002	19	11	21	10
2003	17	13	19	8
2004	24	12	43	13
2005	18	18	32	15
2006	18	12	37	12

Fig. 1. Number of fungi species cumulated for successive 3-year periods of ageing in four studied shelterbelts. Shelterbelt code (S-5a, S-4, S-5b, S-3) see Table 1. Further explanations – see “Materials and methods”.

Because of young age of studied shelterbelts (the oldest one was 14-year old at the end of study and trees planted there – maximum 17 years, because 2–3-year old seedlings were used in shelterbelts), their structure including vegetation cover was markedly changing during the study. The changes concerned mainly herb species composition (Bernacki 2004), tree height, litter amount

and degree of ground shading (Karg 1999, Karg *et al.* 2003, Bernacki 2004).

In particular shelterbelts new macrofungi species were recorded each year, but the pattern of changes in total number of species (observed per 3-year periods) differed between studied shelterbelts (Fig. 1). Increasing trend ($r = 0.77, P < 0.05$) occurred in the shelterbelt S-5a, decreasing trend ($r = -0.89, P < 0.01$) in

S-3, and no clear trends in S-4 and S-5b (r amounted to -0.27 and 0.53 at $P > 0.2$).

A decline in number of species which occurred in 2001–2004 in shelterbelts was most likely caused by drought which reigned in this period during vegetation seasons because marginally significant tendency for increasing of species number with precipitation from April and November occurred ($r = 0.53$, $P < 0.1$).

Changes in species number of macrofungi in relation to plant cover development were studied earlier in different habitats, including tree stands. Most frequently, an increase of species number in early stages of vegetation development was observed (until to age of about 50 years) and then decrease of the number. For example Hintikka (1988) and Termorshuizen (1991) observed such pattern of changes in pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) forest. Keizer and Arnolds (1993, 1994), who studied species composition in oak and beech alleys, also observed increase of species number followed by ageing of trees.

Appearing of different trends which were observed in our study (Fig. 1) was linked most likely with the fact that they covered significantly shorter periods (8 years) than in studied cited above (from several until more than 100 years).

4.2. Similarity of species composition

Similarity of species composition of macrofungi in studied shelterbelts between beginning (1998–2000) and end (2004–2006) of study period was small. Sørensen's similarity index varied between 37 and 46%. According to Tomiałojć (1974), such low value of the

index gives evidence for strong differences in species composition. This strong change was linked most likely with shelterbelt development and with changes undergoing in this habitat. Similarly to these results, significant changes undergoing in group of ectomy-corrhizal species together with forest plant communities development (but concerning much longer period, i.e. several tens years) was described by Last *et al.* (1984), Keizer and Arnolds (1994), Dix and Webster (1995).

Similarity (expressed as the Sørensen's index) between the shelterbelts in first years of their growth (estimated for pairs of 5–7-years old shelterbelts) ranged between 24% (for S-5a and S-4) and 47% (for S-5b and S-4) – in most cases about 40% (Table 3). At the end of study (for age of 9–11 years) the value of Sørensen's index decreased on average from 40 to 34% but the differences was statistically insignificant (Wilcoxon's test: $N = 6$, $T = 3$, $P > 0.1$). Small values of the Sørensen's index resulted mainly from large number of species occurring exclusively in single shelterbelts. Proportion of exclusive species, which occurred in given shelterbelt, amounted to 29–51%. Most of all recorded species (63%) were noted once. For example, some species were observed only in S-4, including *Thelephora caryophyllea* (Schaeff.): Fr. (rare in Poland) growing on soil, *Conocybe albipes* (Oth) Hauskn. occurring on meadows and *Sclerotinia trifoliorum* J. Eriks. which is parasitic species occurring in alfalfa. Two other species – *Typhula filata* (Pers.) Herter (rare in Poland) and *Suillus aeruginascens* (Opat.) Snell. (associated with larch) were found only in S-5b, *Helvella lacunosa* Afzel.: Fr. growing

Table 3. Sørensen's index of similarity (%) of fungi communities between shelterbelts. S-3, S-4, S-5a, S-5b – see Table 1.

Compared shelterbelts	Shelterbelt age (years)		
	5–7	7–9	9–11
S-5a, S-3	43	35	36
S-5a, S-5b	42	39	35
S-5a, S-4	24	31	26
S-3, S-5b	38	42	41
S-3, S-4	45	51	29
S-5b, S-4	47	38	37
Mean	40	39	34

on soil was observed exclusively in S-3, while two other species rare in Poland – *Agrocybe arvalis* (Fr.) Singer and *Ripartites tricholoma* (Alb. & Schwein.: Fr.) P. Karst. occurred only in S-5a. Merely 7% of all species recorded during nine years of study were common for all four shelterbelts. The proportion of those species in relation to number of species recorded in individual shelterbelt ranged between 11 and 32%. Among others there were: ectomycorrhizal *Hebeloma mesophaeum* (Pers.) Quél., in group of humicolous saprotrophs – common in Poland *Agrocybe pediades* (Fr.) Fayod, *Conocybe semiglobata* (Kühner) ex Kühner & Watling and undistinguished in Poland *Macrocystidia cucumis* f. *minor* Joss, among litter saprotrophs – common *Cyathus olla* (Batsch): Pers. and *Hymenscyphus scutula* (Pers.: Fr.) W. Phillips, and among mosses – *Galerina clavata* (Velen.) Kühner observed in only few places in Poland.

Studied community of macrofungi was characterized by significant share of species which fruit bodies appeared ephemerically. As many as 74 species (43%) were observed only once during the study.

In first seven years of shelterbelt development 49 species were noted, which did not occur in next years. There were species characteristic for crop fields and ruderal habitats, e.g. *Agrocybe arvalis* (Fr.) Singer, *Bolbitius titubans* (Bull.: Fr.) Fr., *Clitocybe dealbata* (Sow.: Fr.) P. Kumm., *Coprinus plicatilis* (M. A. Curtis: Fr.) Fr., *Peziza vesiculosa* Bull., *Psathyrella marcescibilis* (Britzelm) Singer or most early appearing mycorrhizal species, e.g. *Inocybe petiginosa* (Fr.) Gillet (Mason *et al.* 1982, Last *et al.* 1984). Disappearing of these species was probably linked with the changes undergoing in course of shelterbelt development, when the share of ruderal plant species and weeds decreases and the share of clearing areas species and typical forest species increases (Bernacki 2004). The changes described above resulted in appearing of species associated clearly with tree communities – as many as 71 (41%) species has appeared not until the eight year or later, among other linked with accumulating litter (e.g. *Auriscalpium vulgare* Gray growing on cones of *Pinus sylvestris* L.), with dead wood (e.g. *Coprinus micaceus* (Bull.: Fr.) Fr., *Exidia plana* (Wiggers) Donk, *Psilocybe* (*Hypholoma*) *fas-*

cicularis (Huds.: Fr.) Noordel.) and mycorrhizal species, classed to a group of so called late-stage fungi (Mason *et al.* 1982, Last *et al.* 1984, Dix and Webster 1995), e.g. *Lactarius quietus* (Fr.) Fr., *L. glyciosmus* (Fr.: Fr.) Fr., *Leccinum scabrum* (Bull.: Fr.) Gray.

Twenty nine species (17%) occurred during almost whole period of investigation. There were species characteristic for synanthropic habitats, e.g. *Agrocybe dura* (Bolt.: Fr.) Singer, *Cyathus olla* (Batsch): Pers., *Marasmius oreades* (Bolt.: Fr.) Fr. and *Psilocybe* (*Stropharia*) *caerulea* (Kreisel) Noordel., as well as species which benefited from the presence of given substrate, e.g. *Collybia cirrhata* (Pers.) Quél., decomposing dead fruit bodies of *Laccaria*, *Marasmius curreyi* Berk. & Broome growing on decaying stalks of grasses, *Galerina clavata* (Velen.) Kühner associated with mosses and mycorrhizal *Suillus grevillei* (Klotzsch: Fr.) Singer and *Xerocomus rubellus* (Krombh.) Quél.

4.3. Biotrophic structure of community

Percentage share of functional groups in particular shelterbelts varied in differentiated way (Fig. 2). For example in group of mycorrhizal species all possible patterns of changes were observed: a) stable, about 30% share in shelterbelt S-5a, b) lack of any trends but strong fluctuations of the share – shelterbelt S-3, c) increasing trend ($r = 0.96$, $P < 0.01$) – from 10 to 20% in shelterbelt S-4, d) decreasing trend ($r = -0.78$, $P < 0.05$) in S-5b. For humicolous saprotrophs the trend of decreasing share of this group ($r = -0.80$, $P < 0.05$) appeared only in the shelterbelt S-3. Total share of fungi growing on soil (M/w and S/s) was highest (60–80%) in all years. For group of litter saprotrophs the pattern of changes was similar to that observed for mycorrhizal species, but only in shelterbelt S-4 decreasing trend was significant ($r = 0.89$, $P < 0.01$). Lignicolous saprotrophs were noted only in two shelterbelts (S-5a and S-3). In the other two shelterbelts no species from this group was observed, what may be explained by the lack of substrate connected with very poor development of trees.

In spite of significant differences between shelterbelts described above, studied fungal communities changed very similarly (with

Fig. 2. Percentage share of biotrophic groups in studied shelterbelts in successive 3-year periods of ageing. Shelterbelt code (S-5a, S-4, S-5b, S-3) see Table 1. Further explanations – see “Materials and methods”.

exception of one shelterbelt) with regard to degree of their structure complexity quantified with the Shannon-Weaver's index H' . The value of the index was increasing during study and the trend was statistically significant (r ranged between 0.94 and 0.96 at $P < 0.05$). The increase was caused by equalization of percentage shares of functional groups occurring in given community (shelterbelt). It means that resistance of studied community functional structure to random negative factors permanently increased during the study.

Similarly to earlier publications by Keizer and Arnolds (1993, 1994) and Dix and Webster (1995) in first years greater share of so-called early-stage species was observed, including e.g. genus *Hebeloma*, *Inocybe*, *Laccaria*, which produce numerous, small fruit bodies. After first several years the late-stage species started to occur, e.g. from genus *Lecanum*, *Lactarius*, *Russula*. Some early-stage species, like *Laccaria proxima* (Boud.) Pat.,

L. laccata (Scop.: Fr.) Berk. & Broome, *Thelephora terrestris* Ehr. ex Willd.: Fr., *Paxillus involutus* (Batsch: Fr.) Fr., co-occurred with late-stage species like *Amanita muscaria* (L.: Fr.) Hook. and *Lactarius necator* (J.F. Gmel.: Fr.) Pers. Similar co-occurrence of pioneer species and those, which are present during long period, was described by Shaw *et al.* (2002) on plots with *Pinus sylvestris* L. and Keizer and Arnolds (1993, 1994) in *Quercus robur* L. alleys. Those latter authors proposed more detailed classification of fungi species into 6 groups characterizing particular stages of natural succession. According to that classification, the studied shelterbelts near Turew could be numbered among first (innovation) and second phase (canopy closure phase). By the criteria accepted by cited authors, the species appearing from first to third phase (aggradation phase) or even fourth (late biostatic phase) belong to separate (sixth) group, so called persistent ectomycorrhizal fungi.

4.4. Rare and threatened species

Some species listed in Red List (Wojewoda and Ławrynowicz 2006) occurred in studied shelterbelts: *Psilocybe (Stropharia) melanosperma* (Bull. ex Pers.: Fr.) Noordel. (E) and *Clavariadelphus fistulosus* (Holmsk.: Fr.) Corner (R), *Thelephora caryophyllea* (V) as well as species unknown from other places in Dezydery Chłapowski Landscape Park, which are rare also in Poland (Wojewoda 2003), e.g. *Agrocybe arvalis* (Fr.) Singer, *Galerina clavata* (Velen.) Kühner, *Lachnella alboviolascens* (Alb. & Schwein.: Fr.) Fr., *Macrocystidia cucumis f. minor* Joss, *Mycena amicta* (Fr.) Quél., *Psilocybe (Stropharia) inuncta* (Fr.: Fr.) Noordel., *Trichophaea gregaria* (Rehm) Boud. and *Typhula filata* (Pers.) Herter. It attests to significant value of young shelterbelts for protection of rare and threatened fungi species. The results of the study broaden the knowledge about ecological niches of some rare species and indicate possibilities of persistence of the species in man-made habitats. At the same time they confirm the importance of planting afforestations as elements, which play significant role in active protection of some fungus species. Earlier, Lisiewska and Strakulska (2002) paid attention to the occurrence of threatened species in substitute habitats – midfield afforestations and to the role of such afforestations for the protection of fungi species diversity in a farmland.

5. CONCLUSIONS

1. Afforestations planted in arable land are colonized by macrofungi as early as in first years of plant cover development. In nine years of study total of 174 species were recorded in four studied shelterbelts.

2. In spite of high similarity of tree stand species composition and similar age, number of fungi species in individual shelterbelts differed statistically significantly. Most likely it is connected with different pattern of herb layer development. In shelterbelts with small number of fungi species the herb layer is formed mainly by grasses, which dense and

compact turf covers almost 100% of the surface.

3. Species composition of fungal communities was changing strongly. The Sørensen's index of similarity between the initial (1998–2000) and terminal (2004–2006) period of investigation derived for given shelterbelts amounted to 37–46%. In spite of high similarity of tree stand species composition (Sørensen's index – 69–80%) in studied shelterbelts, fungal communities differed markedly (Sørensen's index was equal to about 40%).

4. Observed changes in share of functional groups in community differed between studied shelterbelts. However, fungal communities changed similarly concerning general tendency for equalization of functional group shares in communities, what is reflected by increasing trend of H' value. It suggests that resistance of these communities increases during first years of their succession to random, negative effect of environmental factors which can cause disappearing some species.

5. There were recorded rare species listed in Red List of Polish Fungi, e.g. *Psilocybe (Stropharia) melanosperma* (Bull. ex Pers.: Fr.) (E), *Clavariadelphus fistulosus* (Holmsk.: Fr.) Corner (R) and *Thelephora caryophyllea* (Schaeff.): Fr. (V) as well as some species unknown from the other places in the Dezydery Chłapowski Landscape Park and rarely observed in Poland, e.g. *Agrocybe arvalis* (Fr.) Singer, *Galerina clavata* (Velen.) Kühner, *Lachnella alboviolascens* (Alb. & Schwein.: Fr.) Fr., *Macrocystidia cucumis f. minor* Joss, *Mycena amicta* (Fr.) Quél., *Psilocybe (Stropharia) inuncta* (Fr.: Fr.) Noordel., *Trichophaea gregaria* (Rehm) Boud. and *Typhula filata* (Pers.) Herter. It attests to importance of young afforestations for protection of rare and threatened species of fungi in scale of a country.

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